

SOME MANAGEMENT'S ASPECTS REGARDING BALL BEARINGS MINIMIZING SCRAP

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Abstract

Purpose – The work approaches the finding of a good sorting combination, starting from the traditional method of selective assembly, so that the control over the precision classes of the bearings is more precise and obtaining management procedures to minimize the resulting waste.

Methodology/approach - Systemic optimization through a selective assembly method, regarding the control on the radial play of the radial ball bearings.

Findings – Following the application of the selective assembly algorithm, some classifications of the radial clearance in the bearing have resulted, with the help of which some management procedures can be obtained for the reduction of bearing rejects.

Research limitations/implications – Limitations regarding the application of the method over a wide range of dimensions.

Practical implications – Being a wide range of bearing sizes, the proposed algorithm requires a C++ programming language, for the automatic calculation and sorting of the bearing components.

Originality/value – optimization algorithm by the method of selective assembly.

Key words: Ball-bearing, scrap, selective assembly, management.

Introduction

Due to the increase of competition in the global industrial production environment, the complexity and technical requirements of the product require the manufacturing industry a higher and more precise execution, both in the semi-finished stage and in the assembly processes, which results in the finished product.

However, in any series manufacturing process, variation is inevitable, even if it is assumed that the parts and assemblies made are identical. Having a difference from the ideal / theoretical case, there are accepted with certain "visual defects, dimensional, etc." that influence little or not at all how to use the products.

In the present paper, we try to optimize the method of selective assembly in the case of radial ball bearings, with contact at a single point, with application on the initial radial clearance, which results in the accuracy class of the bearings. The radial clearance of a radial ball bearing is modified by mounting, due to tightening adjustments, and in operation, due to thermal expansions.

Starting from the definition of the minimum clearance in the whole ball bearing, we will try to define a procedure for sorting the component elements according to our own execution tolerance, having as reference the selective assembly method, and thus to find the best combination of sort, so that the conditions required by the standard are met and the accuracy classes of the bearings obtained are defined so that their scrap is minimized.

In order to ensure high quality of products in modern enterprises and to meet the demands of users, the Quality Management System (QMS) is widely implemented, which contributes to the competitiveness of

products in the market and to the satisfaction of consumer needs. In bearing industries, there is such a QMS, which involves checks and controls, in all phases and operations of achieving the quality of bearing components.

The method proposed and described below can be considered a management method in the stage before bearing assembly, subsequently following the procedures that are done to control the quality of the bearing assembly. The proposed method can be considered prior to the final control procedures, diminishing from the non-compliant assemblies, in the final phase.

Literature review

The quality of bearings manufacturing is an urgent issue for the machine building industry. The method of sorting the selective assembly involves the execution of the parts at economic tolerances and the sorting of the component elements, on groups of dimensions and later their combination in groups of the same rank, so that the closing element is obtained at the desired precision. The method is only suitable for series production.

The method of selective assembly is applied in the case of size chains, in which the tolerance of the closing element is small, and its distribution, to the dimensions of the chain, leads to very small tolerances, uneconomical to achieve or, in some situations, unachievable. The method is widely used not only for assembling cylindrical parts, but also for more complicated parts. Sometimes, selective assembly acquires an exclusive use, being the only rational method from an economic point of view to increase the precision of assembly (manufacture of bearings, injection pump elements, main shafts from machine tools, etc.). The exposition of the method is made for the chain of dimensions that is formed at a clearance adjustment, where the closing element is the clearance (Georgescu, 2009). This method allows either increasing the quality of the final product or reducing the cost of production to meet customer requirements.

With the rapid development of state-of-the-art computers and advanced measurement technologies over the past decade, selective assembly technology has been frequently applied in many industries, especially in high-precision manufacturing sectors such as micro-production (Löchte, J. Kayasa, C. Herrmann, and A. Raatz, 2012), battery assembly (Sheng Yang, Hui Wang, and Hu, 2013), electrodes for batteries (Schmitt, Raatz, Dietrich, Dröder, and Hesselbach, 2014).

The radial clearance, in its initial state, is established so that, after mounting, under normal temperature conditions, the operating clearance is optimal. If the adjustments are made with increased tightening or the operating temperatures are higher, it is recommended to choose bearings with increased radial clearance (unassembled) (Pop, and Tudose, 2006) (A.B. LLC, 2011).

Kannan and the co-authors (Kannan and Jayabalan, 2001), they proposed a new method of selective assembly, which consists in dividing into two stages of assembly: inner ring-ball, ball-outer ring. In the first stage, they had as references the dimensions of the ball, in order to satisfy the minimum and maximum clearance conditions imposed, and in the second stage they had as reference the group formed in the first stage, also to satisfy the imposed requirements. Their result was the reduction of scrap, from 12,5% by the traditional method of selective assembly, at 8,39% by the method proposed by them, the study being performed on the same dimensions and characteristics.

Kannan and co-authors (Kannan, Asha, and Jayabalan, 2005), proposed an improvement of the selective assembly method for assembling a shaft with a bore, using a genetic algorithm, in order to obtain the best combinations of selective groups, in order to have a minimum variation of the overall clearance. The proposed method was performed in three steps, to use the entire population of mating parts, using a C ++ programming language.

Wang and co-authors (W.M. ; Wang, D. B. # Li, F. & He, and Y. F. Tong, 2018), proposed the approach of a selective assembly scheme for an improved grouping, based on the genetic algorithm (GA), where the elitist strategy was integrated to improve the convergence of the algorithm. The results of their experiments, using the improved GA method, were able to increase the percentage of products assembled from 35,33% at 73,84%.

In their paper (Liu and Liu, 2017), the authors approached the determination of a number of groups for selective assembly, a study conducted on the whole dimensional chain consisting of a main shaft, cylinder, upper bushing and lower bushing. The method consists in dividing into tolerance groups and

grouping the components of the size chain by color codes, so that the assembly results in the technical specifications required by the manufacturer.

In their work, Asha and Babu (Asha and Rajesh Babu, 2017), conducted a study on the variation of tolerance to selective assembly, applying metaheuristic techniques such as Genetic Algorithm (GA), Simulated Annealing algorithm (SAA) and Memetic algorithm (MA). Their case study confirms the proposed approach as more competitive than traditional ones and the reduction of surplus in assemblies.

For enterprises producing bearings for air, rail, automotive and other industries, there is the Technological Process Monitoring System (TPMS), which monitors equipment and parts, processes data on the parameters of monitored objects and makes decisions on process adjustment or machine maintenance, while increasing the quality of the parts (Vahidova et al., 2019), (Osipov, 2011). The program algorithm for diagnosing the inner ring surface uses the Trace mode, which consists in determining the amplitude parameters (reading from the vortex sensor) to identify the deviation max. and min., subsequently the coefficients being compared with the reference characteristics (Samoilova, and Ignatieva, 2015), (Ignatieva, 2015).

In their paper (Yu, Sun, and Geng, 2015), they conducted a study on the quality, inspection and sorting of ball bearings, using an electrical signal system, which is based on the theory of current inspection. The results show that the designed system can detect types of defects such as dimensional, cracks, etc.

Model development management

Grouping method optimization management

Starting from the possibility of a new internal geometric configuration, in which the author D. Săvescu made a study in this regard, in which he came to the conclusion that a different internal geometric configuration is possible, but there are restrictions such as mounting possibilities without elastic deformations, the minimum thickness of the rings is determined by technology (Săvescu, D. 2005), an attempt will be made to obtain an optimization for the selective assembly method, having as reference the new geometric dimensions for the raceways of the rings and the afferent balls.

Figure 1. Geometric parameters for ball bearing

The basic geometric parameters for the radial ball bearing are presented in *Figure 1*: D_a - the outer diameter of the bearing; d_a - the inner diameter of the bearing; P_w - primitive disposal diameter of the rolling bodies; E - external ring rolling-way diameter; F - internal ring rolling-way diameter; D_1 - external ring collar diameter; d_1 - internal ring collar diameter; B_a - width bearing; d_i - inner diameter of the inner ring; B_i - the width of the inner ring; r_i - running radius of the inner ring; D_o - outer diameter of the outer ring; B_o - the width of the outer ring; r_o - running radius of the outer ring; d_b - the ball diameter.

In the standards in force, such as ISO 492: 2014, regarding the dimensional and geometric particularities of the bearings, the internal geometric dimensions are not mentioned, but only some tolerances and deviations, minimum and maximum, in which these bearings should work, in condition unassembled

and at normal temperatures (ISO, 492:2014, 2014). Therefore, each manufacturer has its own "internal kitchen", in which the final product must comply with some final standards of operation.

The first step, for optimizing the selective assembly method, was to determine the primitive diameter with the relation (1), the diameter of the raceways of the 2 rings, inside and outside with the relations (2) and (3).

The improved selective sorting method can be considered a management procedure prior to the Quality Management System, from the final assembly phase, starting from the internal geometry of the bearing, more precisely from the primitive diameter, P_w .

$$P_w = 0.55D_a + 0.45d_a \quad (1)$$

$$E = P_w + d_b \quad (2)$$

$$F = P_w - 2d_b \quad (3)$$

Between the rolling bodies and the raceways there is a clearance that can be radial C_r or axial C_a . This is defined as the average of the possibilities of displacement in radial or axial direction, respectively, of one of the bearing rings in relation to the other held fixed, when their geometric axes are parallel or coincide.

The value of the clearance before mounting the bearing on the shaft or in the housing was called the original clearance. And further on, the study will be done on this type of initial radial clearance, before being mounted, because after mounting the bearing, the clearances change due to the external parameters that appear.

Figure 2. Geometric parameters with MIN and MAX dimensions

To obtain a controlled clearance in the bearing assembly, a selective sorting procedure will be applied and an attempt will be made to obtain a controlled precision class for the bearings. This method can be considered a management procedure, because it is a stage that is performed before the final stage, that

of assembling the bearings, through which their scraps can be minimized and the final quality is increased.

Minimum radial clearance, from the bearing assembly, C_{rmin} , was determined by subtracting the maximum size of the inner ring raceway, F_{max} and two maximum dimensions of the ball diameter, d_{bmax} , from the minimum size of the outer ring raceway, E_{min} , which are given in the equation (4).

$$C_{rmin} = E_{A_{iE}} - F_{A_{sF}} - 2d_b^{A_{sdb}} = A_{iE} - A_{sF} - 2A_{sdb} \quad (4)$$

$$C_{rmax} = E^{A_{sE}} - F_{A_{iF}} - 2d_{b_{A_{idb}}} = A_{sE} - A_{iF} - 2A_{idb} \quad (5)$$

The tolerance of a size is determined by subtracting the minimum size from the maximum size, for example: $\sigma_F = F_{max} - F_{min}$; $\sigma_E = E_{max} - E_{min}$; $\sigma_{db} = d_{bmax} - d_{bmin}$;

In the traditional selective assembly method, the tolerances of the dimensions to be mounted are divided equally, into n groups and subsequently assembled so as to satisfy the final conditions and the reduction of scrap, for example: $\sigma_1 = F_1 + E_1 + d_{b1}$. In Figure 3 is represented the distribution of tolerances in n groups.

Figure 3. Group tolerance for outer race, inner race and ball

The selective assembly variant proposed in this paper, in order to minimize the scrap of bearing components, was to find a convenient sorting method, so that the final requirements are met, the scrap are minimal and also increase the accuracy of the assembly. Therefore, it was found that the most convenient selection for the first group would be the assembly of the outer ring having tolerance from group n , with the inner ring having tolerance from the first group, respectively the tolerance ball from the first group. This has been shown in the equations (6) - (9).

$$\text{Gr. I} \quad C_{rmin} = A_{iEn} - A_{sF1} - 2A_{sdb1} \quad (6)$$

$$C_{rmax} = A_{sEn} - A_{iF1} - 2A_{idb1} \quad (7)$$

...

$$\text{Gr. n} \quad C_{rmin} = A_{iE1} - A_{sFn} - 2A_{sdbn} \quad (8)$$

$$C_{rmax} = A_{sE1} - A_{iFn} - 2A_{idbn} \quad (9)$$

Case study on the management of the optimization of the grouping method

To demonstrate the optimization of the method presented above, we will further analyze a simple radial bearing, with balls on a single row, with contact at a single point. The bearing for analysis is of type 6305 SKF, having the following characteristics: $D_a = 62 \text{ mm}$; $d_a = 25 \text{ mm}$; $B_a = 17 \text{ mm}$;

Starting from the equations (1) - (3), the primitive bearing diameter and the bearing diameters for the two rings were determined:

$$P_w = 0.55D_a + 0.45d_a = 0.55 \times 62 + 0.45 \times 25 = 45.35 \text{ mm}$$

$$E = P_w + d_b = 45.35 + 11 = 56.35 \text{ mm}$$

$$F = P_w - 2d_b = 45.35 - 2 \times 11 = 34.35 \text{ mm}$$

It is assumed that the possibilities and capabilities of the technological process available, for the processing of the components of the bearing and more precisely for the processing of the raceway for the inner ring, F , of the raceway for the outer ring, E and of the rolling element, d_b .

$$E_{A_{iE}}^{A_{sE}} = 56.35_{-0.018}^0 \text{ mm} \rightarrow T=18 \text{ } \mu\text{m};$$

$$F_{A_{iF}}^{A_{sF}} = 34.35_0^{+0.012} \text{ mm} \rightarrow T=12 \text{ } \mu\text{m};$$

$$d_{b_{A_{idb}}}^{A_{sdb}} = 11_{-0.0065}^{-0.0005} \text{ mm} \rightarrow T=6 \text{ } \mu\text{m};$$

These being said, for the dimensional characteristics mentioned above, with the equations (4) and (5) we can calculate the minimum and maximum clearance for the tolerances we can execute, mentioned above. As you can see below, the tolerance between maximum and minimum clearance is quite high, $41 \mu\text{m}$, given that, for example, normal accuracy class for this type of bearing, tolerance is up $15 \mu\text{m}$, according ISO 492:2014.

$$C_{rmin} = A_{iE} - A_{sF} - 2A_{sdb} = 0 - 0 - 2(-0.5) = 1 \text{ } \mu\text{m};$$

$$C_{rmax} = A_{sE} - A_{iF} - 2A_{idb} = 18 - (-12) - 2(-6) = 42 \text{ } \mu\text{m};$$

Next, the above tolerances will be divided into six groups of equal tolerances, as shown in *Figure 3*. The rang for each group was shown in the draws below, respectively $3 \mu\text{m}$ for E , $2 \mu\text{m}$ for F and $1 \mu\text{m}$ for d_b .

$$T_E = 18 \text{ } \mu\text{m} \rightarrow \sigma_E = T_E / 6 = 3 \text{ } \mu\text{m};$$

$$T_F = 12 \text{ } \mu\text{m} \rightarrow \sigma_F = T_F / 6 = 2 \text{ } \mu\text{m};$$

$$T_{db} = 6 \text{ } \mu\text{m} \rightarrow \sigma_{db} = T_{db} / 6 = 1 \text{ } \mu\text{m};$$

Table 1. Division tolerances groups (all value are exprimate in μm)

Group	1		2		3		4		5		6	
	MIN	MAX										
E	0	3	3	6	6	9	9	12	12	15	15	18
F	-12	-10	-10	-8	-8	-6	-6	-4	-4	-2	-2	0
db	-6.5	-5.5	-5.5	-4.5	-4.5	-3.5	-3.5	-2.5	-2.5	-1.5	-1.5	-0.5

Following the equations (6) - (9), simultaneously with the data from *Table 1*, you can calculate the minimum and maximum clearance for each group. All groups will be calculated similarly, and the results are tabulated in *Table 2*. It was found that the accuracy of the adjustment decreases with increasing groups. Therefore, group I would be the least accurate, having a fairly large overall clearance ($MIN=36 \mu\text{m}$ and $MAX=46 \mu\text{m}$), and group VI, would be the most accurate having a very small overall clearance ($MIN=1 \mu\text{m}$ and $MAX=8 \mu\text{m}$).

$$\text{Gr. I} \quad C_{rmin} = A_{iE6} - A_{sF1} - 2A_{sdb1} = 15 - (-10) - 2(-5.5) = 36 \mu\text{m};$$

$$C_{rmax} = A_{sE6} - A_{iF1} - 2A_{idb1} = 18 - (-12) - 2(-6.5) = 43 \mu\text{m};$$

...

$$\text{Gr. VI} \quad C_{rmin} = A_{iE1} - A_{sF6} - 2A_{sdb6} = 0 - 0 - 2(-0.5) = 1 \mu\text{m};$$

$$C_{rmax} = A_{sE1} - A_{iF6} - 2A_{idb6} = 3 - (-2) - 2(-1.5) = 8 \mu\text{m};$$

Table 2. Tolerances resulting from selective grouping (all value in μm)

Gr. I		Gr. II		Gr. III		Gr. IV		Gr. V		Gr. VI	
MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX	MIN	MAX
36	43	29	36	22	29	15	22	8	15	1	8

Following these resulting groups, it was noted that in order to obtain a good precision class, Gr. VI, from the same manufacturing batch, with the mentioned dimensional deviations, the best selective sorting was the assembly of the outer rings from Gr. n (having the largest dimensional deviations), together with the inner rings from Gr. 1 (having the smallest dimensional deviations) and with the balls from Gr. 1 (having the smallest dimensional deviations).

Figure 4. New tolerance groups resulting from selective assembly

Figure 5. Diagram with dividing tolerances

In *Figure 4*, the tolerance diagram of the resulting groups was presented, following the selective assembly method. It can be seen that the tolerance distribution of the new resulting groups is similar to the tolerance of the inverted *E* bodies, as the above method was presented.

In *Figure 5*, a diagram represented here with the distribution of tolerances on the six largest groups, having as reference the zero line, for the assembly of the three elements *E*, *F*, *db*. It can be seen that it can be reduced to a minimum for *E* and *F* is below the reference line, the deviation for *db* is above the reference line.

Conclusions

Also, through this management procedure, based on the sorting of the component elements according to their tolerance, it was found that it is possible to have a control over obtaining the dimensional deviation from the ball-bearings.

Compared to ISO precision classes of radial ball bearings, of *Table 3*, where *C2* is the most accurate class and *C5* the least accurate, it can be seen that the groups obtained with this optimized selective method can fit on the same principle of grouping from ISO 492:2014. (*Gr. I – C5; Gr. II – C4; Gr. III – C4; Gr. IV – C3; Gr. V – N; Gr. VI – C2*).

This method was also tried for its assembly *E* only with positive deviation, with *F* only with negative deviation and *d_b* only with negative deviation, but the result was that in one group the minimum game was negative.

It tried to assemble and selection of *E* positive, with *F* negative and *d_b* with intermediate deviation, but even in this case, the maximum clearance for one of the groups was negative.

Table 3. Accuracy classes. Extract from ISO 492:2014

d (mm)		C2 (μm)		N (μm)		C3 (μm)		C4 (μm)		C5 (μm)	
>	≤	min	max	min	max	min	max	min	max	min	max
24	30	1	11	5	20	13	28	23	41	30	53

The results obtained in this paper will be passed to a next stage, in a Mathcad programming language, to identify the possibilities of developing, verifying and implementing the sorting method, at parameterized level, for different types of bearings.

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